
Instagram Forum @Genrejateng_ As A Media For Youth Education

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ABSTRACT: Instagram is one of the most popular digital platforms at the moment as evidenced by data from We are Social February (2022) Instagram occupies the second position as the most used social media with a percentage of 84.8% of the total number of social media users in Indonesia. This has made many users, both individuals, organizations and community groups, utilizing Instagram media as an educational medium, including the Planning Generation Forum (GenRe) organization in Central Java Province which utilizes the Instagram media account @genre_jateng as one of the social media used for social media. educational media for audiences, especially for teenagers. The Instagram account @genre_jateng functions to convey education and information regarding the activities of the Genre program under the auspices of the BKKBN and as a means of public communication. The results of the study show that the types of educational information conveyed in Instagram and live streaming content are related to Genre programs, activities carried out, commemorations of national and international holidays, education related to handling problems faced by adolescents, as well as information for the general public. Feedback based on likes and comments on each content is still very rare or minimal.

KEYWORDS: Instagram, Central Java Genre Forum, Education, Teenager.

A. INTRODUCTION

We are Social (2022) noted that as of February 2022 there were around 191.4 million active social media users or around 68.9% of the 277.7 million population in Indonesia. Instagram is one of the social media that is popular among people around the world and Indonesia as a media platform that presents various visual products, Instagram is a social media platform that has 1.45 billion active users every month throughout the world in April 2022 (Rizaty and Bayu, 2022). According to data presented in the online article DataIndonesia.id in October 2022, the number of Instagram users in Indonesia reached 93.6 million people, this large number makes Indonesia rank fourth in the world. In Indonesia, it is currently evident from data according to We are Social February (2022) that Instagram is in second place as the most favorite social media used in Indonesia. Whatsapp 35.2%, Instagram 22.9%, Facebook 13.1%, Tiktok 9.1%. The ease of using the Instagram application means that the Instagram platform can be used by its users as a medium for educational information and is something that is very natural for today's young people (Sari & Basit, 2020).

Several previous studies show that Instagram can be used as an educational medium, such as a journal with the title "Using Instagram Social Media as an Educational Effort to Prevent the Spread of COVID-19" written by Muhammad Irfan Fauzi and Nova Yulianti in 2021. This research discusses the use of Instagram social media @Cimahikota as an educational effort to prevent the spread of COVID-19 by Cimahi city government public relations. The second journal is a journal with the title "Use of Instagram in Socializing the Movement to Save Pedestrians (Study of the Pedestrian Coalition Community)" written by Lilis Ramadhanti and Yugih Setyanto in 2018. This research discusses the use of Instagram by the Pedestrian Coalition community in socializing the movement Save Pedestrians. The third journal is a journal with the title "Analysis of the Use of Instagram @dearcallers.id as a Media to Create Awareness Regarding the Issue of Catcalling Against Women in Indonesia" written by Monica Elvira in 2021. This research discusses the Instagram account @dearcallers.id and how this account works. can educate and increase awareness of the issue of Catcalling in Indonesia through managing four steps in the Practical Media Model and sharpened with Social Information Processing.

Based on several journals above, researchers want to conduct research related to the use of Instagram social media as an educational medium for teenagers, this is because the number of teenagers who use Instagram tends to be large. Data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) shows that Indonesia's youth population will be 64.92 million people in 2021, which is 23.90% of Indonesia's total population (Mahdi, 2021). For Instagram users with an age range of 13-24 or in the teenage age category, that is 19.8% of the total population of internet users in Indonesia. One of the problems of teenagers in Central Java that is of serious concern is the rate of early marriage which tends to increase every year. Early marriage is a marriage that occurs when both partners wishing to get married have not yet reached adulthood or if one of the partners is still under the age of 18 (Rahayu & Wahyuni,

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2020). This is supported by data presented in the online article Merdeka.com (22/04/2022) in 2019 cases of marriage of girls under 19 years old showed that there were 3,726 children, in 2020 this increased to 11,301 children, and in 2021 it increased again to 11,686 children.

To address problems among teenagers, the Indonesian government has prepared various efforts, including through the Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection (KEMENPPPA) and developed by the National Population and Family Planning Agency (BKKBN) by establishing the Planning Generation program or what is commonly known as the GenRe program (DISKOMINFO JEMBER DISTRICT, 2021). The existence of the Generasi Plan program created the GenRe Forum (Plan Generation), the Genre Forum in Central Java is part of the Indonesian Genre Forum which was formed to serve and educate teenagers with the aim of helping young people in Indonesia, especially in Central Java, become a young generation that is protected the risk from Triad KRR (Sexuality, HIV/AIDS, Narcotics, Psychotropics and Addictive Substances) (Yulianti, 2017).

Implementation of this program can be done using various intermediary media such as social media which is closely related to current technological advances. According to Fujiawati and Raharja (2021), social media is online-based media that is used to meet the needs of interaction, communication, sharing and participating in creating content that is used by account owners or users through certain applications with internet network access that can connect fellow users in sufficient areas. broad and can involve the public both for discussion, forming a forum, sharing information and other education.

This makes it natural that Instagram was chosen as one of the social media that can be utilized because Instagram, which is an application launched by Kevin Systrom and Mike Krieger in 2010, succeeded in attracting 25,000 people on the first day (Atmoko, 2012). This is no exception to the Central Java Genre Forum which has an Instagram account @genre_jateng where the Forum's management can include members ranging from Genre Ambassadors selected from various districts in Central Java province to members of PIK-R and PIK-M who meet the criteria for Genre Forum membership. Central Java which is divided according to divisions as a medium for educational information and public communication. Instagram itself comes from the abbreviation of the words "instant telegram" which is a social networking application based on photography at first but as the application develops, Instagram now comes with a unique presentation of various features such as a camera equipped with filters that can be adjusted to the user's tastes, editing menus, feeds, Instagram stories, reels, live streaming on Instagram, IG TV, Direct Messages or menus to communicate either in writing or messages, voice notes, telephone or video calls.

Teenage life and social media today are still an interesting discussion, especially the target of the Generation Planning program through representatives of Genre Ambassadors with the substance raised in the Genre program itself, namely free sex, HIV/AIDS, Marriage Age Maturation, NAPZA, Life Skills, 8 Family Functions, Gender, KIE/Advocacy. namely teenagers aged 10-24 years (BKKBN, 2012). This is what makes researchers want to know how members of the Central Java Genre Forum manage and convey educational information related to the campaign to raise the age of marriage and calls for a ban on free sex on the Instagram account @genre_jateng. Research on how to use Instagram @genre_jateng in efforts to educate teenagers in Central Java is the latest research to be carried out. It is hoped that this research will add new insights and variations as a complement to research with similar themes that has been carried out previously.

B. METHODS

The method chosen in research must be appropriate to the problem being studied, so researchers use descriptive qualitative methods. Research with a descriptive nature aims to provide a clearer depiction of social situations (Mulyadi, 2001). Data is certainly an important component in research. There are two types of data, namely primary and secondary data. Arikunto (2013) defines primary data as data collected through first parties, usually through interviews, operations, etc. The main data for this research are the results of interviews with sources and data sought from researchers. In contrast to primary data, where data is obtained directly from the source or subject being researched, secondary data is data obtained from other sources, such as books or previous research. According to Sugiyono (2012), secondary data is a source of data obtained through reading, learning and understanding through other media, obtained from literature, books and documents. The research subjects in this research are the parties behind the Instagram account @genre_jateng.

In accordance with the research method applied, namely the qualitative method used in the research and the type of data is primary data, the data collection technique is the interview method. An in-depth interview is an interaction/conversation between one person being interviewed and one informant (Manzilati, 2017). Apart from interviews, observational research methods will also be used. According to Susanto (2015), the observation method is a data collection technique that requires researchers to be involved in the lives of the people being studied. The observations carried out by the author are participant observations, namely the author carries out the observation process by becoming part of the life of the research object to obtain accurate results by following the Instagram account @genre_jateng to directly observe the activities carried out by the Instagram account. To strengthen the data obtained during the research, researchers also used the document method in their data collection techniques. According to Widoyoko (2015), the concept of documentation is divided into two meanings, namely narrow meaning and broad meaning. This research uses pictures, reports and diaries as well as library research.

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In this research, researchers used a purposive sampling technique to select informants. Purposive sampling is taking data sources using certain criteria, in other words people who are considered to have the most knowledge to represent the data to be collected (Sugiyono, 2012). After the data is obtained, a data analysis method is needed. After analyzing the data, it is necessary to validate the data so that the data obtained is valid data. One method that can be used to validate data is triangulation. According to Sutopo (2006), triangulation is the most commonly used method to increase the validity of qualitative research data. There are various types of triangulation, one of which is primary triangulation which is used by researchers as a method to determine the validity of data in a study. Source triangulation is the verification and comparison of information obtained from different sources, for example comparing interview results with observations.

C. DISCUSSION

The research results obtained by the author in this study are the result of research using interview techniques, observation and documentation through public access data provided by the Instagram account @genre_jateng via bit.ly/AksesPublikGenreJateng which is available in the Instagram bio column of the @genre_jateng account.

Picture 1.0 Instagram account logo @genre_jateng

Source: https://www.instagram.com/genre_jateng

The Instagram account logo @genre_jateng is a combination of the genre greeting logo with one of the components of the Central Java provincial service logo. The Central Java Province Genre (Plan Generation) Forum was officially established on March 8 2018 as a youth empowerment organization which is overseen by representatives of the Central Java Province BKKBN and is a partnership (Pre-Research Documentation based on the Central Java Genre AD-ART Report), however, the Central Java Genre has They previously had an Instagram social media account, namely since June 26 2016. Apart from that, they also manage several other social media such as YouTube, Spotify and TikTok. Through the Planning Generation Forum, teenagers in Central Java will be provided with information and education regarding skills and life skills, important reproductive health issues, counseling services and KRR referrals so that teenagers can have a planned future and also achieve family life in the future (Aziz, 2021).

The process of delivering educational information is also closely related to public communication carried out through the media used. According to Nasution (2020), public communication is the process of exchanging messages with many people who are members of a group, both internal and external, either directly or through the media. Communicators and sources in public communication dominate and the delivery also uses common language so that listeners can understand it. The aim of public communication is to provide information to the public regarding organizational activities and the organization's production results as well as establishing relationships between organizations and communities outside the organization (Nasution, 2020).

UU no. 52 of 2009 Chapter III Part One Article 5 Point C explains that in the process of implementing population development and family development, citizens in Indonesia have the right to receive information, protection and assistance to realize reproductive rights in accordance with social ethics and religious norms (JDIH regulations database BPK RI), this can make the GenRe program one of the programs launched to help with community development and development problems, especially among teenagers, by helping convey information related to programs designed by BKKBN either through direct outreach or through social media.

Instagram is a social media that allows users to search for various information related to culinary, fashion, education, apart from that, Instagram can also allow anyone to upload various content according to the account owner's goals, in the form of feeds, reels, IG TV, live streaming. The ease of accessing content from the social media Instagram has made many users and certain communities use Instagram as a medium for educational information and public communication, one of which is the Central Java Province Genre Forum (Plan Generation). Instagram as social media is a medium in cyberspace that allows users to interact in communication with other users, forming virtual social bonds (Sari & Basit, 2020).

Based on the results of an interview with the head of the media and publication team division, Annisa Aqil Saputri, who is currently still a student at Semarang State University, explained that the Central Java Genre Forum has social media Instagram as a medium for conveying educational information and public communication related to activities and programs carried out by the

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Forum. Central Javanese Genre. The @genre_jateng Forum account is an online forum for the Central Java Genre Forum administrators to interact with a wide audience, especially teenagers in Central Java province.

Picture 2.0 Display of the Instagram profile of the @genre_jateng account

Source: https://www.instagram.com/genre_jateng

The @genre_jateng Instagram account does not have a specific target for how many followers it has, but currently the @genre_jateng account already has 26.3 thousand followers with the number of content uploads reaching 1,462 since 2016, both in the form of photos and videos. Based on the appearance of the Instagram account profile @genre_jateng, it explains that Genre Central Java is a professional account that is included in the Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) category, which is a social movement that focuses on empowering youth in Central Java.

According to Yunus, et al (2015) education is a series of efforts carried out and desired through the provision of knowledge or information which can later influence other people, both individuals, families, groups and communities so that they can live their lives in a planned way. Education via Instagram by the media and publications team, according to the head of the division team who is usually called Kak Aqil, was deemed quite effective in conveying the objectives of the Central Java Genre Forum program. This is because through the insight feature on Instagram, media and publications team managers can see the extent of attention received, obtained from the content they create, both in feeds and genre talk shows which are carried out via live Instagram streaming.

The Instagram account @genre_jateng is managed by the media and publications division team of the Central Java Genre Forum, which consists of 4 people. The head of the media and publications division team has the authority to ensure coordination between media and publications division staff is effective and efficient, carry out control mechanisms for achieving targets for the media and publications division, coordinate with the chairman of the Central Java Genre Forum regarding decisions to be taken by the team, be responsible on performance results to the chairman and regional congress.

The duties of the media and publication team division staff, totaling 3 people consisting of Hasbi Fajar Qodri, Muhammad Nur Arif, Rinjani Khanza Safira, are responsible for the production of creative content based on social media, YouTube, websites, creating designs for organizational needs, creating internal designs. Developing social media, publishing activities related to Central Java Genre activities, establishing mass media partners.

The Central Java Genre Forum uses Instagram as one of the official social media because Instagram is considered a contemporary social media that is widely used by many audiences. This is also supported by data from We are Social (2022), where currently Instagram is ranked second as the most widely used social media with an age range of internet users 16-64 years, amounting to 84.8%.

Based on the results of interviews with the media team and the target publication of the @genre_jateng Instagram account, it is more towards teenagers, especially in Central Java, but it does not rule out the possibility that there are followers of this account who are over 24 years old asking or interacting regarding Genre Central Java's programs and activities. Via the comments column or DM (Direct Message) you will still get the same response because this media is also a public communication media as long as the question is still within the boundaries of the Central Java Genre Forum area.

The content available on the @genre_jateng Instagram account feeds consists of several content categories such as activity genre content, genre talk show or previously known as genre talk, genrepedia or genre info which is a summary or educational information related to BKKBN's Genre program activities, or activities carried out by the Central Java Genre Forum. For genre quizzes, this is usually done after completing the genre talk show material, the genre award will be done when there is a competition

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with certain themes related to the genre program, usually related to each performance, idea and campaign for the genre program from each district genre forum in Java. Middle, the celebration genre is used as educational information related to the commemoration of national and international days such as World AIDS Day which is celebrated every December 1.

Picture 3.0 Display Feeds of Instagram account content @genre_jateng

Source: https://www.instagram.com/genre_jateng

It can be seen from the appearance of the feeds that the content created by the media and publication team has a plan. Apart from that, the @genre_jateng account also has highlights which are a collection of Instagram stories related to information and education which are grouped in different spaces so that followers can easily find the information they need. The content planning and editing are made entirely by the media and publication team, but when it is published they will first coordinate the content that will be posted on social media with the chairman of the Central Java Genre Forum and other teams in monthly meetings because every month the Forum has an agenda. monthly meetings which can discuss both monthly performance evaluations and next month's work plans that will be implemented.

Based on joint interviews with the media and publications division team, they have a monthly agenda for content on Instagram as a reference for the performance of the Instagram media management team, namely the media and publications division team. Although in practice, if there is a shift in the content update schedule, this is something that is very likely to happen due to unexpected situations such as the busyness of each team member, but the team leader feels that this will not be an obstacle to Instagram media management activities because later if the person responsible cannot Carrying out the tasks they are carrying out will be coordinated via the team's WhatsApp group to carry out assignments.

Picture 4.0 Monthly Content Calendar Instagram account @genre_jateng (Genre Jateng public access document)

Source: https://www.instagram.com/genre_jateng

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Based on Figure 4.0, you can see the monthly content calendar timeline or content upload planning for each week of the month, although it is not explained that there are daily upload targets and content upload time schedules. Basically, determining the upload time is also important to determine high engagement and to be able to reach the audience or followers more optimally (Priadana & Murdiyanto, 2020).

Based on observations, the educational content received the most attention from followers of the @genre_jateng Instagram account, seen from the number of views when they conducted genre talk shows with trusted sources and likes on several genrepedia posts and genre awards.

Picture 5.0 one of Genrepedia's posts on the @genre_jateng account.

Source: https://www.instagram.com/genre_jateng

Through the description of the Genrepedia post on the @genre_jateng account, followers or followers of the Genre Jateng Instagram media can find out what actions are included in risky dating behavior. As an effort to keep teenagers away from having sex before marriage, it is not uncommon for the media and publication management team to also include sentences of advice or invitations on the last slide or in the caption column to emphasize the educational information they are conveying.

Picture 6.0 Genrepedia's Slide

Source: https://www.instagram.com/genre_jateng

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The Central Java Genre Forum also uses #genrekanjateng which is placed in their Instagram bio and in each caption as one of the movement's efforts to invite teenagers in Central Java to become teenagers who plan or teenagers who have a planned future and do not fall into activities that are damaging their future such as free sexual behavior or early marriage without proper preparation.

The media and publication team explained that the Instagram account @genre_jateng utilizes professional features or what is usually called a business account feature in the NonGovernmental Organization (NGO) category which focuses on empowering youth in Central

Java, among other things, so that they can see insights or information based on follower demographics and content. uploaded which has several characteristics, including the Activity feature which is a tool for recording interactions from followers who provide feedback (Alfajri et al, 2019). Feedback in this case is usually in the form of likes, comments, saves or shares which serve as the basis for followers' attention to the content created. This insight also has a content feature which allows all data from the posting feature, stories in the form of photos and videos to be saved and the audience feature is used to understand the characteristics of followers on the @genre_jateng account, this is because through this feature the management team can find out media and publications to see how many followers there are, location of followers, gender of followers, how old followers are and even when followers are active on Instagram, usually in the form of audience demographics (Alfajri et al, 2019).

The Central Java Genre Forum management media and publication team makes it easier to carry out media monitoring with the Instagram insight feature in reporting feedback from each content as an evaluation activity carried out every month, other activities such as monitoring DM (Direct Messages) entered into the @genre_jateng account also as a medium for interacting with followers or followers who may feel reluctant to ask questions via the comments column both on posts and live streaming during genre talk shows.

According to the results of an interview with the head of the media and publications team, it was explained that at one time the media and publications team, after coordinating to upload a piece of content when it had been posted, apparently the content was content that was deemed sensitive enough to be discussed, so many followers suggested that the post be taken down in various ways. consideration makes the suggestions conveyed to the media and publication team via direct messages become good feedback and it is felt that they can help the media and publication team a little in managing their social media content to be even better.

Researchers saw that in every post, in all categories of content created by the @genre_jateng account, the response from followers of the @genre_jateng account was still minimal, this was due to a discontinuity between the number of followers and the like response to each piece of content. The highest number of likes is only less than 700 likes, while comments are almost rarely found, however, for video posts in the form of education via live Instagram content or live Instagram videos of genre talk shows with experts or videos of Central Java Genre Forum activities that have been saved, some have a range of The audience reached 14 thousand.

Picture 7.0 Genre's Talkshow Poster

Source: https://www.instagram.com/genre_jateng

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The theme of a talk show genre is also felt by the media and publication team to influence the level of engagement. To see the engagement activities carried out by the media team and the publication of the @genre_jateng account, you can also search for the hashtags #Genrejateng #GenRekanJateng #CreateTheHistory. Until now, the most engaging events for followers have been in the form of quizzes, where as appreciation for the best answers, they will be reposted in the story of the @genre_jateng account.

D. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it was found that the management of the Central Java Genre Forum's social media, especially the Instagram account @genre_jateng, is fully managed by the media and publications team division, which consists of 4 people, from the chairman to the staff. The media and publication team has a monthly plan for uploaded content even though it is not explicitly explained what time of day and time it will be uploaded. All team members work together to help each other to manage the Central Java Genre social media in turns from content creation, editing to caption writing and are carried out under the responsibility of the media and publication division team of the Central Java Genre Forum which is chaired by Aqil.

The educational content created in each media is related to activities carried out in empowerment and programs from genres that have been adapted to material from BKKBN such as efforts to prevent early marriage, information about the negative impacts that will occur due to free sex, how to toxic relationships and solutions to avoid them. or getting out of unhealthy relationships like that and there is much more material related to teenagers so that they are empowered to become teenagers who plan. For the media and publication team, interaction with followers is really felt when doing genre talk shows because at that moment the audience can ask questions directly to the experts who are the main sources or speakers in the talk show. Even though the number of followers they have is quite large, it seems that responses to comments and likes are still very rare or even few. It is not uncommon for the comments made to be also not in accordance with the topic being discussed. This means that the Instagram account @genre_jateng is not visible so much as the feedback felt from each Uploaded educational content in the form of photo feeds or saved videos or live streaming videos.

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